

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

AN INSTRUMENTAL EARTHQUAKE CATALOGUE FOR THE OFFSHORE MALTESE ISLANDS REGION, 1995–2014

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In this supplementary material, find examples of earthquake waveforms which were classified as quality B and C (Figures [S1](#) and [S2](#)), the earthquake time series sorted by distance from station WDD, longitude and latitude (Figure [S3](#)), and the compiled earthquake catalogue for the Malta region from 1995 to 2014 (Figure [S4](#), white box, and Table [S1](#)).

Classified quality B earthquakes which are not listed in the IRIS and INGV are included in the earthquake catalogue. Quality C earthquakes are excluded from the catalogue.

Earthquakes locations and magnitude in the catalogue may have significant inaccuracies. Please read Section [2.2](#) and see Figures [5](#) and [6](#).

Figure S1: Example of a quality ‘B’ seismogram. Recording of an earthquake on the 5th of October 2011 at 06:33:16 (UTC) located by ING V at 35.79°N 15.26°E with a magnitude of 2.7 (M_L), 68 km east of Malta. Top 3 waveforms are the HHE, HHN and HHZ filtered components followed by the back-azimuth (0–360°) and coherence estimates (0–1) respectively. Rows 6–10 and 11–15 are the corresponding waveforms and estimates for BH and LH streams, respectively. O, P, S, and F mark the origin time, the arrival of the *P* and *S* phases, and the end of the earthquake, respectively. The estimated back-azimuth at the *P* phase arrival for the HH, BH and LH are indicated on top. This seismogram is rated as quality B because despite a clear earthquake waveform the *P*-wave polarization of the three streams disagree significantly. Hence, the waveform is considered of poor quality and is listed so in the earthquake catalogue (e.g., Figures 7 and S4, and Table S1).

Figure S2: Example of a quality ‘C’ seismogram. Same as Figure S1 but for what is presumably an earthquake on the 21st of May 2013 at 02:20:00 (UTC) which is not located by INGV or IRIS. This seismogram is rated as quality C because of its very poor signal making it difficult to pick the *P* phase. Events of Quality C waveforms and which are not listed by other bulletins are not listed in the earthquake catalogue.

Figure S3: Earthquake time series of the merged bulletins sorted by distance from seismic station WDD, longitude and latitude. Each circle represents a unique earthquake. Red and pink circles are good and poor earthquake locations processed using single-station analysis (S.Sta.), respectively, whereas grey circles are locations from network solutions (Net., INGV and IRIS). The coloured horizontal lines mark the data availability for the different channels of station WDD.

Figure S4: The seismicity in the Sicily Channel from 1995–2014. Circles are unique earthquake epicentres located either by regional networks INGV or IRIS (grey), or by single-station (red and pink) *P*-wave polarisation analysis on station WDD (green triangle). The size of each circle corresponds to the magnitude of the earthquake. Red circles are robust locations; pink are poor locations. Thick and thin blue contours mark the depth at every 1000 and 200 metres, respectively. White box indicates the study region considered for the Malta earthquake catalogue (Table S1). Inset map shows the area on a regional map.

Table S1: List of earthquakes for the Malta region from 1995 to 2014. **Note:** Earthquakes locations and magnitudes may have significant inaccuracies. Please read Section 2.2 and see Figures 5 and 6. The columns represent the origin time, longitude, latitude, depth, magnitude, and solution.

Origin time	Longitude (°E)	Latitude (°N)	Depth (m)	Magnitude	Solution
1995-03-11T19:10:14.290000Z	14.486	35.277	10000.0	3.1	Network
1995-08-09T12:39:39.781000Z	14.285	35.690		2.7	Single station (poor)
1996-04-04T02:47:30.905000Z	15.286	35.772		3.0	Single station (poor)
1996-06-08T01:31:19.310000Z	15.210	35.751	10000.0	3.2	Network
1996-06-24T00:33:08.899000Z	15.652	36.222		2.9	Single station (poor)
1996-08-05T01:11:57.910000Z	16.119	34.864	10000.0	3.1	Network
1996-08-09T04:14:26.421000Z	14.415	35.647		2.3	Single station
1996-08-10T00:27:41.164000Z	14.601	35.645		2.6	Single station
1996-08-19T23:25:56.500000Z	15.260	34.810	0.0	3.6	Network
1996-10-27T16:16:52.160000Z	15.048	34.405	146070.0	3.3	Network
1996-11-16T21:44:58.950000Z	15.254	36.085	10000.0	3.4	Network
1997-01-16T11:08:29.212000Z	15.387	34.604		3.2	Single station (poor)
1997-01-27T17:09:23.840000Z	14.245	36.338	10000.0	2.6	Network
1997-02-06T13:00:53.516000Z	13.582	35.073		3.4	Single station (poor)
1997-04-24T18:05:47.657000Z	14.754	36.006		2.1	Single station (poor)
1997-04-30T16:09:33.724000Z	14.509	35.665		2.5	Single station
1997-05-01T11:08:45.496000Z	14.583	35.675		2.3	Single station
1997-05-02T22:36:34.705000Z	14.471	35.653		3.6	Single station
1997-08-18T03:57:34.813000Z	14.549	34.966		3.3	Single station (poor)
1997-11-17T11:41:07.910000Z	14.629	35.674		3.1	Single station
1998-01-08T21:23:12.213000Z	14.535	35.577		2.3	Single station
1998-01-09T01:57:04.042000Z	15.775	35.692		2.7	Single station (poor)
1998-02-22T01:05:07.506000Z	15.438	34.126		3.4	Single station (poor)
1998-02-22T13:13:32.146000Z	15.853	35.926		3.1	Single station
1998-05-10T22:24:03.085000Z	14.938	35.002		3.4	Single station
1998-06-02T17:13:17.827000Z	14.470	35.560		2.3	Single station (poor)
1998-06-02T17:45:22.348000Z	14.867	35.878		1.8	Single station (poor)
1998-06-08T21:57:37.045000Z	15.443	36.097		3.0	Single station (poor)
1998-07-08T08:44:56.890000Z	14.374	35.488	10000.0	3.0	Network
1998-07-12T15:10:05.744000Z	14.169	35.666		3.6	Single station
1998-07-14T02:27:14.590000Z	14.821	35.582		2.4	Single station
1998-07-19T16:25:20.326000Z	14.991	35.045		2.9	Single station
1998-09-18T05:24:56.577000Z	14.525	35.249		2.9	Single station (poor)
1998-10-09T14:52:49.651000Z	14.223	35.624		2.9	Single station (poor)
1998-11-05T11:11:56.270000Z	14.490	36.181		2.8	Single station (poor)
1998-11-05T18:16:08.415000Z	14.136	35.683		2.5	Single station (poor)
1998-11-21T01:03:19.609000Z	13.668	36.164		3.3	Single station (poor)
1999-03-28T21:46:22.410000Z	14.151	36.346	5000.0	3.2	Network
1999-05-04T02:25:28.300000Z	15.898	35.039	10000.0	3.1	Network
1999-05-13T03:29:58.123000Z	16.110	35.293		3.1	Single station (poor)
1999-05-30T23:16:23.024000Z	14.609	34.627		2.6	Single station
1999-06-20T04:21:06.136000Z	15.120	34.603		3.2	Single station (poor)
1999-07-04T02:16:06.818000Z	15.344	35.531		2.1	Single station
1999-08-11T16:10:55.907000Z	13.685	34.945		2.9	Single station (poor)
2000-01-19T16:21:26.620000Z	13.972	34.503	10000.0	4.1	Network
2000-01-20T15:55:00.740000Z	14.101	34.309	5000.0	3.3	Network
2000-02-09T02:04:21.640000Z	13.853	36.190	10000.0	2.9	Network
2000-02-27T22:42:23.823000Z	13.816	34.562		2.8	Single station (poor)
2000-02-28T04:24:38.558000Z	13.590	34.673		3.9	Single station
2000-03-25T09:30:38.491000Z	14.655	35.635		2.3	Single station
2000-04-21T17:36:41.653000Z	13.912	35.691		4.0	Single station
2000-04-27T08:36:38.680000Z	14.029	35.602	10000.0	3.6	Network
2000-04-28T17:30:57.644000Z	14.435	36.309		3.0	Single station (poor)

2000-05-01T01:32:48.629000Z	13.854	34.993		2.9	Single station (poor)
2000-05-05T05:32:40.355000Z	14.149	35.354		2.9	Single station (poor)
2000-05-11T22:38:11.625000Z	14.943	34.866		2.7	Single station
2000-05-20T14:49:46.798000Z	14.634	35.615		1.9	Single station
2000-06-23T17:08:18.758000Z	13.895	35.747		2.8	Single station (poor)
2000-06-29T08:53:29.219000Z	13.629	34.890		3.0	Single station
2000-08-17T01:40:34.416000Z	14.666	34.767		2.8	Single station
2000-08-17T02:13:09.729000Z	14.937	34.794		4.0	Single station
2000-08-17T05:10:11.451000Z	14.905	34.815		3.6	Single station
2000-08-18T15:15:04.976000Z	14.976	35.170		2.6	Single station
2000-08-20T08:21:39.035000Z	14.572	34.777		3.0	Single station
2000-08-21T14:19:09.840000Z	14.932	34.807		3.6	Single station
2000-08-26T20:51:15.635000Z	16.422	35.105		2.9	Single station (poor)
2000-09-02T00:30:38.678000Z	14.833	34.206		3.7	Single station
2000-09-02T00:49:44.283000Z	13.683	34.365		3.8	Single station (poor)
2000-09-02T06:35:19.361000Z	14.052	34.328		3.8	Single station
2000-09-03T00:42:59.983000Z	14.696	34.218		3.8	Single station
2000-09-03T01:34:03.788000Z	15.871	34.955		2.9	Single station (poor)
2000-09-03T04:10:22.722000Z	15.913	34.586		3.3	Single station
2000-09-03T06:25:51.147000Z	13.816	34.101		3.2	Single station (poor)
2000-11-12T22:11:57.112000Z	14.100	36.253		2.4	Single station
2000-11-18T19:59:20.962000Z	14.506	35.662		2.9	Single station
2000-11-20T08:45:57.800000Z	13.548	35.977	10000.0	3.0	Network
2000-11-21T08:47:04.129000Z	14.410	35.692		2.4	Single station
2000-11-23T22:14:34.271000Z	14.529	35.665		2.2	Single station
2000-11-28T16:40:34.433000Z	14.464	35.693		2.5	Single station
2000-12-06T00:24:53.671000Z	14.382	35.704		2.2	Single station
2000-12-17T13:52:52.395000Z	14.371	35.754		2.2	Single station
2001-02-03T04:18:20.675000Z	14.577	35.732		2.9	Single station
2001-02-14T04:20:36.072000Z	14.428	35.712		2.1	Single station
2001-02-14T08:31:46.003000Z	14.135	34.925		3.6	Single station
2001-03-07T20:26:26.278000Z	15.034	35.023		3.8	Single station
2001-03-08T15:17:13.844000Z	14.490	34.932		3.3	Single station
2001-03-10T22:12:57.235000Z	14.899	34.950		3.3	Single station
2001-03-12T17:02:52.450000Z	14.604	34.968		3.0	Single station
2001-03-23T01:03:35.847000Z	14.579	34.927		3.4	Single station
2001-03-26T10:13:19.386000Z	14.163	35.007		3.9	Single station
2001-03-26T14:51:13.860000Z	14.761	34.922		3.2	Single station
2001-03-30T11:27:29.923000Z	15.278	35.100		3.7	Single station
2001-03-31T02:51:03.827000Z	14.710	34.955		3.2	Single station
2001-04-03T22:14:38.547000Z	14.995	35.010		2.7	Single station
2001-04-05T02:59:19.682000Z	14.845	34.972		2.8	Single station
2001-04-15T11:21:29.110000Z	14.829	34.982		3.3	Single station
2001-04-20T01:35:30.023000Z	14.391	35.011		3.4	Single station
2001-04-20T12:04:52.538000Z	15.162	35.032		3.8	Single station (poor)
2001-04-23T13:49:51.274000Z	14.720	35.011		3.4	Single station
2001-04-24T02:39:32.291000Z	14.675	34.989		3.0	Single station
2001-04-24T07:19:56.821000Z	15.337	35.268		3.2	Single station (poor)
2001-04-25T05:01:18.838000Z	14.323	34.893		3.0	Single station (poor)
2001-04-25T05:05:26.671000Z	14.705	35.022		3.1	Single station (poor)
2001-04-25T23:06:25.672000Z	14.884	34.963		3.0	Single station
2001-04-26T00:34:09.334000Z	15.122	34.984		3.3	Single station
2001-04-26T17:53:03.566000Z	14.301	34.914		3.1	Single station
2001-04-28T04:02:43.930000Z	14.225	35.196	10000.0	3.2	Network
2001-05-19T13:53:38.882000Z	14.216	34.969		3.7	Single station
2001-06-03T06:43:26.403000Z	15.013	34.858		3.4	Single station
2001-06-03T17:24:07.613000Z	14.463	34.934		2.4	Single station

2001-06-07T20:11:16.652000Z	14.803	34.890		3.8	Single station
2001-06-09T07:40:38.790000Z	15.019	34.865		3.2	Single station
2001-06-19T15:12:38.563000Z	14.912	34.972		3.2	Single station
2001-06-23T01:01:57.750000Z	15.449	34.837		3.1	Single station
2001-07-09T10:56:23.414000Z	14.174	34.416		3.4	Single station (poor)
2001-08-14T18:29:15.401000Z	14.646	34.819		2.9	Single station (poor)
2001-08-18T10:02:14.894000Z	14.001	34.819		3.1	Single station (poor)
2001-08-19T10:14:46.479000Z	14.444	34.788		3.3	Single station
2001-08-19T18:26:46.086000Z	14.409	34.753		3.4	Single station
2001-09-07T14:31:14.416000Z	14.560	34.852		3.3	Single station
2001-10-17T19:16:46.543000Z	14.911	34.957		2.7	Single station (poor)
2002-03-01T17:50:38.452000Z	14.348	35.236		3.3	Single station
2002-04-06T13:13:00.750000Z	14.558	36.108	10000.0	3.1	Network
2002-06-15T12:32:30.470000Z	14.163	35.937	10000.0	3.0	Network
2002-06-20T01:26:28.430000Z	15.094	36.313	9698.0	3.6	Network
2002-08-08T14:58:19.094000Z	14.546	36.016		3.2	Single station
2002-08-17T04:04:50.364000Z	15.238	35.356		2.8	Single station (poor)
2002-08-19T01:22:12.802000Z	14.735	35.495		2.1	Single station (poor)
2002-10-26T14:51:06.895000Z	14.817	34.109		4.1	Single station
2002-12-21T07:55:49.743000Z	14.740	35.058		3.1	Single station (poor)
2002-12-22T00:37:02.327000Z	14.536	34.462		3.3	Single station (poor)
2003-02-07T23:16:57.451000Z	15.883	34.724		3.5	Single station
2003-05-09T04:45:41.142000Z	14.619	35.916		1.5	Single station
2003-06-06T03:37:29.596000Z	14.197	35.637		2.2	Single station (poor)
2003-06-11T13:29:29.602000Z	13.673	34.922		3.1	Single station (poor)
2003-06-24T14:36:07.299000Z	14.788	34.508		3.5	Single station
2003-07-07T15:08:14.303000Z	14.763	36.043		4.6	Single station
2003-08-07T17:00:03.768000Z	14.640	34.868		3.5	Single station
2003-08-22T03:27:38.750000Z	14.697	35.618		2.0	Single station (poor)
2003-08-24T01:09:58.850000Z	13.935	36.161	10000.0	3.2	Network
2003-09-08T14:32:42.040000Z	15.723	35.480		3.5	Single station
2003-09-14T02:22:12.187000Z	15.706	34.752		4.2	Single station
2003-10-26T19:05:02.751000Z	14.861	34.992		3.0	Single station
2003-11-05T01:52:39.833000Z	14.549	36.028		2.1	Single station
2003-11-19T03:10:02.058000Z	15.262	35.230		3.1	Single station (poor)
2003-12-22T23:35:44.883000Z	14.594	35.112		3.3	Single station
2004-01-21T17:43:20.337000Z	14.141	34.913		4.7	Single station
2004-04-11T00:37:27.750000Z	15.116	35.152	10000.0	3.2	Network
2004-07-19T10:12:30.700000Z	14.645	35.032		3.4	Single station
2004-09-04T01:59:42.020000Z	14.680	34.335		2.8	Single station
2004-09-10T00:54:24.100000Z	14.847	34.475	10000.0	3.4	Network
2004-09-10T16:13:33.044000Z	15.139	34.883		3.4	Single station
2004-09-11T01:24:27.607000Z	15.158	34.801		3.2	Single station
2004-09-15T17:32:09.197000Z	14.563	34.686		3.4	Single station
2004-09-27T23:37:44.030000Z	14.342	35.024		3.3	Single station
2004-09-29T21:55:11.419000Z	16.190	34.705		3.2	Single station (poor)
2004-12-15T06:59:20.629000Z	15.835	35.823		4.4	Single station
2004-12-20T21:39:16.729000Z	14.196	34.667		3.7	Single station
2005-01-06T16:25:31.631000Z	14.552	34.525		3.3	Single station
2005-01-15T01:08:38.232000Z	14.917	34.912		3.8	Single station
2005-01-17T04:29:59.194000Z	14.665	34.907		3.9	Single station
2005-02-01T14:47:27.842000Z	13.930	34.831		4.3	Single station
2005-03-03T08:56:04.882000Z	14.182	34.941		3.0	Single station
2005-04-22T15:40:48.611000Z	15.309	35.435		4.3	Single station
2005-05-09T10:55:45.699000Z	15.399	36.011		2.9	Single station (poor)
2005-05-30T21:09:13.292000Z	14.581	34.952		2.9	Single station
2005-05-30T21:19:37.361000Z	15.538	35.941		2.9	Single station

2005-05-30T22:06:09.499000Z	14.332	34.951		2.4	Single station
2005-06-09T02:12:13.425000Z	15.793	35.886		3.0	Single station (poor)
2005-06-26T03:12:03.006000Z	13.529	34.930		3.2	Single station
2005-07-11T23:27:42.784000Z	14.701	36.373		2.6	Single station
2005-07-16T05:35:12.949000Z	13.853	35.122		3.0	Single station (poor)
2005-07-16T21:47:32.920000Z	14.792	34.395		2.6	Single station (poor)
2005-07-16T23:45:16.910000Z	14.616	34.566		3.4	Single station
2005-07-16T23:47:34.880000Z	14.805	34.589		3.6	Single station
2005-07-17T01:50:57.810000Z	14.814	34.507		3.4	Single station
2005-07-17T02:48:31.918000Z	15.064	34.475		2.6	Single station
2005-07-17T03:10:35.220000Z	13.545	34.606		2.8	Single station (poor)
2005-07-18T11:45:41.995000Z	15.161	34.551		3.4	Single station
2005-07-25T22:06:02.540000Z	15.177	35.174		2.7	Single station (poor)
2005-08-18T01:40:30.052000Z	14.861	35.080		2.2	Single station (poor)
2005-08-29T21:19:33.770000Z	16.141	36.200	9100.0	3.0	Network
2005-09-04T18:07:32.777000Z	14.114	34.780		2.7	Single station (poor)
2005-09-04T18:59:38.110000Z	15.640	35.533	12500.0	3.2	Network
2005-09-05T08:14:09.331000Z	13.877	35.451		2.3	Single station (poor)
2005-09-27T10:24:32.425000Z	14.162	34.944		3.3	Single station
2006-04-16T05:17:53.260000Z	15.912	35.249	10000.0	2.7	Network
2006-05-18T04:03:46.696000Z	15.025	35.905		1.9	Single station (poor)
2006-05-18T16:10:04.374000Z	14.704	36.164		2.4	Single station
2006-05-19T13:27:00.680000Z	15.183	36.201	10000.0	2.4	Network
2006-06-28T19:39:44.390000Z	14.571	35.225	10000.0	2.9	Network
2006-06-29T07:54:15.840000Z	14.676	35.564	10000.0	3.1	Network
2006-08-09T10:38:50.050000Z	13.890	36.077	10000.0	2.7	Network
2006-08-16T02:47:45.080000Z	14.707	35.815	18400.0	2.9	Network
2006-10-25T02:03:11.480000Z	13.711	35.061		2.2	Single station
2006-10-27T20:27:40.507000Z	15.109	34.761		3.2	Single station
2006-10-29T03:24:41.784000Z	14.051	34.845		2.7	Single station
2006-11-20T01:49:26.170000Z	13.715	34.629	10000.0	3.5	Network
2006-11-24T04:37:40.416000Z	15.748	36.262		4.9	Single station
2006-11-25T18:56:54.445000Z	15.773	36.082		3.4	Single station
2006-11-25T19:04:52.796000Z	15.733	36.194		2.6	Single station
2006-12-13T13:28:57.558000Z	15.004	34.502		3.5	Single station
2006-12-21T05:29:51.420000Z	16.442	35.918	10000.0	3.2	Network
2007-01-04T10:07:39.744000Z	14.860	35.627		2.5	Single station
2007-01-04T15:08:22.774000Z	15.221	34.824		3.3	Single station
2007-01-07T12:04:13.868000Z	14.968	34.739		2.9	Single station
2007-01-25T08:28:35.610000Z	14.661	34.913		3.1	Single station
2007-01-26T15:15:35.415000Z	15.206	35.097		2.9	Single station
2007-01-26T23:35:46.777000Z	14.728	34.925		3.6	Single station
2007-01-27T00:52:51.327000Z	14.385	34.937		2.9	Single station (poor)
2007-01-27T01:21:57.795000Z	14.596	34.953		2.5	Single station
2007-01-27T02:08:37.819000Z	14.708	34.887		2.5	Single station (poor)
2007-01-27T02:23:34.225000Z	15.188	35.080		2.7	Single station (poor)
2007-01-27T23:03:15.976000Z	14.736	34.953		3.4	Single station
2007-02-03T11:38:39.196000Z	14.898	34.971		3.3	Single station
2007-02-06T04:23:58.175000Z	15.129	35.091		2.7	Single station (poor)
2007-02-06T12:16:52.881000Z	15.347	35.201		3.0	Single station
2007-02-06T17:40:13.696000Z	14.732	34.960		3.2	Single station
2007-02-11T17:11:52.210000Z	16.097	35.081		4.2	Single station
2007-02-15T04:26:22.592000Z	14.962	35.661		3.2	Single station
2007-02-18T07:32:06.740000Z	15.173	36.358	10000.0	2.7	Network
2007-03-06T06:19:21.093000Z	14.752	35.621		2.5	Single station
2007-03-13T01:26:03.720000Z	14.046	36.359	10000.0	2.7	Network
2007-03-22T12:18:58.393000Z	14.269	35.564		2.6	Single station

2007-03-30T13:59:47.933000Z	14.371	35.548		2.4	Single station (poor)
2007-03-31T12:22:32.330000Z	13.724	34.601	10000.0	4.3	Network
2007-03-31T13:08:01.306000Z	14.196	34.555		3.5	Single station
2007-04-06T22:43:17.193000Z	14.104	34.691		2.6	Single station (poor)
2007-04-19T00:35:10.477000Z	15.581	35.570		2.6	Single station
2007-04-23T21:59:18.010000Z	14.660	35.997	10000.0	2.3	Network
2007-05-01T02:09:06.909000Z	14.793	34.849		2.6	Single station (poor)
2007-05-08T01:05:44.084000Z	14.911	35.612		2.2	Single station (poor)
2007-05-11T03:29:56.680000Z	14.522	35.429		2.2	Single station (poor)
2007-05-11T12:56:30.035000Z	14.021	34.378		3.3	Single station
2007-05-12T13:11:29.668000Z	13.557	35.121		2.5	Single station (poor)
2007-06-21T04:44:09.716000Z	13.546	35.113		2.9	Single station
2007-06-24T16:13:05.799000Z	14.581	35.507		2.0	Single station
2007-07-13T16:25:10.934000Z	15.423	34.546		3.2	Single station
2007-07-13T22:21:38.903000Z	16.277	36.380		2.7	Single station (poor)
2007-08-11T02:19:07.320000Z	14.148	35.572	36200.0	2.8	Network
2007-08-16T01:51:28.184000Z	14.779	35.700		2.2	Single station
2007-08-23T20:38:51.780000Z	14.657	35.701	10000.0	2.8	Network
2007-08-30T22:18:21.789000Z	14.688	36.077		1.9	Single station (poor)
2007-09-03T01:08:44.602000Z	13.583	34.983		2.8	Single station
2007-09-05T06:36:03.022000Z	14.261	35.610		2.9	Single station
2007-09-05T06:59:24.403000Z	14.265	35.638		2.4	Single station (poor)
2007-09-05T07:58:12.509000Z	14.423	35.582		2.5	Single station (poor)
2007-09-05T08:02:48.872000Z	14.271	35.617		3.0	Single station
2007-09-05T09:21:52.816000Z	14.712	35.593		2.3	Single station
2007-09-20T03:01:31.394000Z	15.271	34.644		3.0	Single station (poor)
2007-10-03T02:15:08.589000Z	14.868	35.793		1.7	Single station (poor)
2007-10-15T17:36:44.017000Z	14.685	35.129		3.9	Single station
2007-11-02T04:47:05.803000Z	14.671	36.198		2.4	Single station
2008-01-13T20:28:11.438000Z	13.737	35.007		3.0	Single station (poor)
2008-01-14T11:10:06.255000Z	14.694	34.893		2.8	Single station
2008-01-16T00:30:06.362000Z	14.541	35.933		1.6	Single station
2008-01-16T05:04:15.761000Z	14.538	35.930		2.0	Single station
2008-02-11T08:05:38.692000Z	14.569	35.156		2.8	Single station (poor)
2008-02-13T11:34:54.329000Z	14.088	34.512		3.1	Single station (poor)
2008-02-24T10:58:23.665000Z	13.773	35.292		3.3	Single station
2008-02-24T19:03:29.144000Z	14.501	35.658		2.0	Single station
2008-03-06T14:29:31.710000Z	14.019	36.282	10000.0	2.9	Network
2008-05-06T05:19:11.603000Z	14.651	34.876		2.7	Single station
2008-05-18T12:11:06.060000Z	13.728	35.156		3.1	Single station (poor)
2008-06-17T01:56:41.551000Z	16.204	35.191		3.1	Single station
2008-07-08T06:12:58.876000Z	13.842	36.130		3.2	Single station
2008-07-24T00:56:25.101000Z	14.971	36.362		3.7	Single station
2008-08-01T15:22:32.211000Z	14.654	34.993		3.4	Single station
2008-08-12T09:23:16.840000Z	15.170	35.532		2.5	Single station (poor)
2008-08-16T02:55:10.704000Z	14.053	35.042		2.8	Single station (poor)
2008-08-22T02:54:18.976000Z	14.614	34.370		3.0	Single station
2008-08-26T04:10:42.620000Z	14.753	36.350	10000.0	2.5	Network
2008-08-28T05:05:22.505000Z	13.814	34.877		3.0	Single station
2008-09-08T08:11:18.905000Z	15.137	35.023		2.5	Single station (poor)
2008-10-24T06:02:00.609000Z	14.083	35.366		2.6	Single station (poor)
2008-11-30T16:28:26.663000Z	14.903	35.665		2.8	Single station (poor)
2008-12-02T18:42:18.866000Z	13.518	36.099		2.8	Single station (poor)
2008-12-16T02:30:18.898000Z	16.479	36.309		3.9	Single station (poor)
2008-12-17T03:02:42.432000Z	13.782	35.673		2.8	Single station (poor)
2008-12-23T23:47:23.824000Z	14.844	35.591		2.2	Single station (poor)
2008-12-25T18:52:52.706000Z	14.056	34.584		3.1	Single station (poor)

2009-01-11T02:46:22.146000Z	15.588	34.395		3.2	Single station (poor)
2009-02-05T03:55:22.999000Z	15.875	35.832		3.5	Single station
2009-02-18T07:38:06.450000Z	14.811	35.510		2.4	Single station
2009-02-20T13:45:49.410000Z	15.682	35.573	5000.0	2.8	Network
2009-03-23T18:44:35.810000Z	13.759	34.475		4.3	Single station
2009-04-17T07:40:10.267000Z	14.804	36.045		1.9	Single station (poor)
2009-04-25T01:36:24.815000Z	14.618	34.250		4.7	Single station
2009-04-28T02:56:39.772000Z	14.756	35.616		2.8	Single station
2009-04-28T03:35:25.072000Z	14.876	35.856		2.6	Single station (poor)
2009-05-02T09:27:25.679000Z	14.691	35.574		2.9	Single station
2009-05-07T22:35:52.670000Z	14.638	36.141	8800.0	2.2	Network
2009-05-16T13:08:43.022000Z	14.557	35.957		2.6	Single station
2009-05-20T13:39:13.899000Z	14.691	35.011		2.2	Single station (poor)
2009-05-20T14:31:15.193000Z	14.815	34.850		2.7	Single station
2009-05-20T16:01:48.975000Z	14.849	34.973		2.8	Single station
2009-05-21T01:46:30.421000Z	15.170	35.031		2.2	Single station
2009-05-21T01:52:37.283000Z	14.758	34.943		2.2	Single station (poor)
2009-05-21T01:59:09.753000Z	15.555	35.998		2.0	Single station (poor)
2009-05-21T02:24:57.628000Z	14.264	34.926		2.2	Single station (poor)
2009-05-21T02:41:12.739000Z	14.401	34.892		3.3	Single station
2009-05-21T02:58:16.278000Z	14.347	34.851		2.3	Single station (poor)
2009-05-21T03:17:45.751000Z	15.276	35.133		2.7	Single station
2009-05-21T03:19:43.673000Z	15.531	35.397		2.6	Single station
2009-05-24T13:54:51.726000Z	15.505	34.836		3.0	Single station
2009-05-26T21:17:54.129000Z	14.854	34.958		2.8	Single station
2009-05-26T21:37:19.934000Z	13.559	35.248		2.9	Single station
2009-05-26T21:49:04.370000Z	15.171	35.095	10000.0	2.4	Network
2009-05-29T10:25:20.963000Z	14.726	34.575		2.9	Single station
2009-07-05T18:52:14.903000Z	13.588	35.048		3.4	Single station
2009-07-14T20:01:49.817000Z	14.730	36.047		1.8	Single station (poor)
2009-07-15T19:52:23.333000Z	14.954	35.697		1.6	Single station
2009-07-29T19:30:03.070000Z	15.124	35.041	9700.0	3.0	Network
2009-07-29T21:58:25.170000Z	14.864	35.037	9200.0	3.1	Network
2009-07-30T02:22:05.063000Z	13.995	35.032		2.3	Single station
2009-07-30T02:58:35.640000Z	15.155	35.022	9900.0	3.0	Network
2009-07-30T05:38:54.460000Z	15.143	35.110	10000.0	3.3	Network
2009-07-30T06:10:46.986000Z	14.733	34.920		2.8	Single station (poor)
2009-08-07T09:06:22.894000Z	14.972	35.908		3.4	Single station
2009-08-08T19:52:51.126000Z	14.941	35.915		1.8	Single station (poor)
2009-08-16T07:49:42.778000Z	14.676	34.962		3.0	Single station
2009-08-25T03:21:04.853000Z	15.584	36.141		2.4	Single station (poor)
2009-08-25T20:53:09.705000Z	13.852	35.055		2.9	Single station (poor)
2009-08-29T03:34:07.178000Z	13.632	35.416		2.9	Single station
2009-08-29T20:53:47.361000Z	13.793	35.232		2.6	Single station
2009-08-29T22:37:57.368000Z	13.721	35.115		3.0	Single station
2009-09-01T17:45:12.151000Z	13.661	35.155		3.0	Single station
2009-09-02T01:30:31.529000Z	15.752	35.988		2.9	Single station (poor)
2009-10-01T06:04:37.050000Z	13.700	35.386	10000.0	2.8	Network
2009-10-02T00:05:33.630000Z	13.812	35.528	10000.0	3.2	Network
2009-10-18T08:06:09.670000Z	14.720	35.014	10000.0	3.6	Network
2009-12-20T04:33:34.613000Z	13.981	34.690		3.6	Single station
2009-12-26T20:49:11.234000Z	14.156	34.533		3.1	Single station (poor)
2009-12-31T15:00:18.675000Z	13.580	34.683		3.5	Single station
2010-01-03T00:39:00.141000Z	14.280	34.551		3.5	Single station (poor)
2010-01-04T01:50:40.988000Z	13.772	34.570		3.1	Single station
2010-01-04T06:29:01.141000Z	14.397	34.539		3.5	Single station
2010-01-05T11:23:22.521000Z	15.583	34.274		4.1	Single station

2010-02-16T06:42:16.341000Z	14.010	35.158		3.9	Single station
2010-02-16T12:06:02.634000Z	13.911	35.171		3.4	Single station
2010-02-17T07:54:25.528000Z	13.849	35.246		3.1	Single station (poor)
2010-02-20T00:41:19.356000Z	13.878	35.265		2.8	Single station (poor)
2010-02-24T14:44:20.993000Z	13.950	35.052		2.8	Single station
2010-02-26T16:38:49.985000Z	14.219	34.382		3.0	Single station
2010-03-12T07:26:09.674000Z	14.756	35.667		2.3	Single station (poor)
2010-03-21T11:54:13.304000Z	15.405	35.506		2.7	Single station (poor)
2010-03-30T01:54:05.781000Z	14.393	34.799		2.8	Single station (poor)
2010-04-01T16:15:14.817000Z	15.450	35.107		2.6	Single station (poor)
2010-04-16T03:20:26.478000Z	13.658	35.575		2.3	Single station (poor)
2010-04-18T09:38:27.157000Z	14.473	35.499		2.9	Single station
2010-04-21T03:46:40.053000Z	13.506	35.249		3.0	Single station
2010-04-27T07:45:05.925000Z	14.715	35.072		3.4	Single station
2010-04-27T18:48:23.643000Z	15.047	35.210		2.4	Single station
2010-05-23T22:04:07.320000Z	15.009	35.444	10000.0	2.6	Network
2010-06-05T21:19:11.088000Z	13.603	35.104		2.9	Single station
2010-06-15T23:29:24.068000Z	14.309	35.522		2.2	Single station (poor)
2010-06-18T01:38:08.430000Z	13.566	35.694	10000.0	2.3	Network
2010-06-22T23:46:36.150000Z	15.707	35.113	10000.0	3.1	Network
2010-06-25T23:05:28.687000Z	14.709	34.614		2.8	Single station (poor)
2010-06-28T22:26:06.855000Z	14.785	35.466		2.4	Single station
2010-07-03T18:11:35.960000Z	14.970	36.133	10000.0	2.2	Network
2010-07-03T19:06:05.421000Z	14.852	35.574		2.2	Single station
2010-07-08T05:00:30.606000Z	13.623	34.110		3.7	Single station
2010-07-08T05:20:01.474000Z	13.683	34.018		2.7	Single station (poor)
2010-07-09T00:19:24.936000Z	14.451	34.800		3.4	Single station
2010-07-09T12:46:28.746000Z	14.243	34.769		3.1	Single station
2010-07-11T22:58:36.017000Z	13.560	34.205		3.5	Single station
2010-07-11T23:26:57.220000Z	13.873	36.319	7200.0	2.6	Network
2010-07-13T11:19:32.418000Z	13.906	34.301		3.9	Single station
2010-07-13T13:18:54.698000Z	14.165	34.822		2.8	Single station
2010-07-13T23:30:00.452000Z	14.301	34.239		2.7	Single station (poor)
2010-07-14T00:35:35.695000Z	13.504	34.306		3.5	Single station
2010-07-14T00:55:48.983000Z	13.742	34.343		2.8	Single station
2010-07-15T17:38:45.246000Z	13.896	34.266		3.3	Single station
2010-07-21T02:21:21.084000Z	13.592	35.336		2.5	Single station (poor)
2010-07-26T01:48:24.270000Z	16.449	35.251	0.0	3.6	Network
2010-07-27T14:03:09.680000Z	14.556	36.329		2.3	Single station (poor)
2010-08-03T08:06:48.892000Z	14.300	35.533		2.5	Single station (poor)
2010-08-11T15:59:03.580000Z	15.028	36.286	10000.0	2.9	Network
2010-08-21T09:21:47.854000Z	14.539	35.382		1.8	Single station
2010-09-12T06:30:36.920000Z	14.311	34.291		3.1	Single station (poor)
2010-09-18T06:47:07.521000Z	15.054	34.103		3.4	Single station
2010-09-21T04:39:43.116000Z	14.758	35.267		2.6	Single station
2010-09-22T17:07:32.245000Z	14.717	36.081		2.2	Single station
2010-10-23T00:54:48.310000Z	14.975	36.393	7000.0	2.8	Network
2010-10-24T09:53:48.772000Z	14.504	34.772		3.0	Single station (poor)
2010-11-10T08:22:43.734000Z	14.555	35.034		4.2	Single station
2010-11-12T04:43:35.272000Z	14.686	35.064		4.3	Single station
2010-11-15T08:28:39.709000Z	13.859	35.296		2.6	Single station (poor)
2010-11-18T08:20:09.623000Z	14.646	35.072		3.7	Single station
2010-11-19T19:24:58.009000Z	14.640	35.035		3.7	Single station
2010-11-19T19:45:56.683000Z	14.156	35.155		2.6	Single station
2010-11-23T03:38:51.346000Z	14.496	36.098		2.6	Single station (poor)
2010-12-01T11:41:52.777000Z	15.123	34.392		4.5	Single station
2010-12-03T02:02:20.384000Z	14.576	35.453		2.8	Single station

2010-12-05T00:28:06.454000Z	14.089	34.872		3.2	Single station
2011-01-05T12:22:18.642000Z	14.128	35.720		2.3	Single station (poor)
2011-02-15T23:11:13.884000Z	14.660	35.293		2.6	Single station (poor)
2011-02-17T15:03:59.860000Z	14.522	35.551		3.3	Single station
2011-03-09T10:37:18.769000Z	15.076	35.054		3.0	Single station
2011-03-27T23:57:41.435000Z	14.568	35.695		2.1	Single station
2011-03-30T21:06:01.910000Z	15.049	36.083	10000.0	2.5	Network
2011-04-04T21:29:20.576000Z	14.645	35.735		1.7	Single station
2011-04-04T21:39:19.473000Z	14.605	35.732		1.5	Single station
2011-04-23T20:35:21.780000Z	13.603	36.334	30000.0	2.8	Network
2011-04-23T22:10:58.563000Z	14.898	35.966		3.6	Single station
2011-04-24T01:34:01.052000Z	14.935	35.874		3.2	Single station
2011-04-24T02:44:34.591000Z	14.821	36.106		2.3	Single station
2011-04-24T03:29:07.663000Z	14.924	35.873		2.6	Single station
2011-04-24T04:25:40.155000Z	14.921	35.947		2.6	Single station
2011-04-24T04:39:00.060000Z	14.921	35.875		3.1	Single station
2011-04-24T09:21:19.096000Z	14.908	35.975		3.7	Single station
2011-04-24T09:25:28.798000Z	14.891	35.960		3.5	Single station
2011-04-24T09:33:07.193000Z	14.726	36.139		2.4	Single station (poor)
2011-04-24T09:57:58.230000Z	14.893	35.842	10000.0	2.6	Network
2011-04-24T13:02:12.376000Z	14.942	35.914		4.4	Single station
2011-04-25T00:02:36.728000Z	14.715	36.168		2.4	Single station
2011-04-25T06:10:19.580000Z	14.922	35.881		3.0	Single station
2011-04-26T04:10:29.202000Z	14.944	35.764		3.3	Single station
2011-04-26T18:00:13.970000Z	14.834	36.024		2.6	Single station (poor)
2011-04-27T05:40:38.538000Z	14.784	36.098		2.7	Single station (poor)
2011-05-08T13:29:43.930000Z	14.587	35.741	7100.0	2.7	Network
2011-05-11T15:17:12.204000Z	14.622	35.731		3.4	Single station
2011-05-17T19:55:25.856000Z	14.685	35.501		2.3	Single station (poor)
2011-05-17T23:16:49.716000Z	14.513	35.713		2.0	Single station
2011-06-21T12:09:51.493000Z	13.883	35.581		2.5	Single station
2011-06-23T06:50:34.790000Z	14.013	35.448	10000.0	2.7	Network
2011-07-04T00:22:01.608000Z	13.813	34.964		2.8	Single station
2011-07-08T18:15:12.655000Z	13.532	35.174		2.5	Single station (poor)
2011-07-25T07:10:42.815000Z	15.663	34.983		3.0	Single station
2011-07-28T09:45:44.193000Z	14.686	34.753		2.9	Single station (poor)
2011-08-04T17:14:48.777000Z	13.930	36.104		2.2	Single station (poor)
2011-08-07T04:01:56.000000Z	16.440	35.780	10000.0	0.7	Network
2011-08-08T05:05:38.864000Z	14.635	35.264		2.1	Single station (poor)
2011-08-08T15:37:25.500000Z	15.832	36.386	14900.0	2.4	Network
2011-08-12T09:10:19.531000Z	14.707	35.196		2.6	Single station
2011-08-12T11:15:42.980000Z	15.814	34.996	10000.0	3.1	Network
2011-08-19T00:39:36.803000Z	13.601	35.094		2.5	Single station
2011-08-20T13:27:40.610000Z	14.992	35.651		2.0	Single station
2011-08-21T05:54:27.019000Z	14.454	35.378		2.5	Single station
2011-08-25T15:14:30.568000Z	14.112	34.923		2.7	Single station
2011-08-26T05:39:33.276000Z	14.223	35.603		2.7	Single station
2011-08-28T15:33:48.929000Z	13.667	34.921		3.8	Single station
2011-08-28T19:14:50.441000Z	13.577	34.908		3.2	Single station (poor)
2011-08-30T16:28:29.192000Z	14.201	34.723		2.8	Single station (poor)
2011-09-02T11:02:36.271000Z	14.597	35.704		1.9	Single station
2011-09-04T13:31:19.784000Z	14.319	35.489		2.6	Single station
2011-09-09T17:05:23.628000Z	14.820	34.673		2.9	Single station
2011-09-13T09:40:52.693000Z	15.590	34.579		3.2	Single station
2011-09-17T00:53:21.764000Z	14.734	35.990		1.6	Single station (poor)
2011-09-21T03:26:40.089000Z	13.996	35.016		3.0	Single station
2011-09-28T17:21:49.330000Z	13.593	35.504		2.6	Single station (poor)

2011-10-05T06:33:16.580000Z	15.263	35.789	21700.0	2.7	Network
2011-10-26T07:15:50.507000Z	14.095	34.812		3.9	Single station
2011-10-26T10:36:33.114000Z	14.002	34.835		2.8	Single station
2011-11-08T14:50:32.540000Z	13.622	34.117	10000.0	3.5	Network
2011-11-16T06:40:34.138000Z	14.960	35.331		3.9	Single station
2011-11-16T08:09:05.739000Z	14.108	35.319		3.1	Single station (poor)
2011-11-26T17:10:05.062000Z	15.425	34.757		3.6	Single station
2011-11-27T00:43:55.780000Z	16.015	35.199	10000.0	3.0	Network
2011-12-02T12:21:11.030000Z	15.505	34.734		2.9	Single station
2012-02-03T08:25:57.824000Z	13.981	34.708		3.9	Single station
2012-03-23T10:28:14.348000Z	13.599	34.474		4.3	Single station
2012-03-24T01:18:58.273000Z	13.885	34.975		2.7	Single station
2012-03-27T02:29:35.826000Z	14.904	35.171		3.0	Single station
2012-03-30T19:54:09.130000Z	13.626	34.663	10000.0	3.9	Network
2012-05-25T00:35:09.620000Z	14.952	35.914	10000.0	2.9	Network
2012-06-01T09:40:16.699000Z	15.473	34.832		3.1	Single station (poor)
2012-06-05T12:30:11.061000Z	14.205	34.975		3.0	Single station
2012-06-05T14:14:51.614000Z	14.962	36.061		1.9	Single station (poor)
2012-07-03T05:03:41.710000Z	14.498	34.059		5.4	Single station
2012-07-03T05:59:41.739000Z	14.575	34.130		3.7	Single station
2012-09-09T04:59:10.333000Z	14.447	34.731		2.5	Single station
2012-09-18T04:17:59.052000Z	14.714	36.115		2.0	Single station (poor)
2012-09-24T23:35:01.994000Z	14.367	34.832		3.3	Single station
2012-09-25T17:53:35.327000Z	14.358	34.468		3.1	Single station
2012-10-02T03:42:00.114000Z	14.729	36.117		2.6	Single station
2012-10-04T07:28:53.146000Z	14.157	34.851		3.4	Single station
2012-10-11T06:46:55.620000Z	15.865	36.156	10000.0	2.4	Network
2012-10-16T17:02:08.089000Z	14.174	34.854		3.8	Single station
2012-10-23T19:26:40.061000Z	15.283	34.408		3.2	Single station
2012-10-25T16:41:33.209000Z	15.059	34.865		2.9	Single station
2012-11-18T05:03:07.474000Z	14.982	35.790		2.4	Single station (poor)
2012-11-20T05:25:12.843000Z	14.895	34.245		3.8	Single station
2012-12-12T22:49:58.390000Z	13.847	36.152	17500.0	2.8	Network
2012-12-28T16:23:29.925000Z	14.541	35.725		3.4	Single station
2013-01-03T11:29:58.640000Z	13.611	36.315	28300.0	3.0	Network
2013-01-08T01:27:05.910000Z	15.862	34.926	10000.0	3.2	Network
2013-01-30T09:48:56.499000Z	14.497	36.137		2.5	Single station
2013-01-30T11:30:56.658000Z	14.373	36.108		2.7	Single station
2013-03-08T15:52:05.810000Z	13.884	36.336	10400.0	2.3	Network
2013-03-13T07:04:29.243000Z	13.774	35.387		3.1	Single station (poor)
2013-03-13T16:00:12.978000Z	15.235	35.359		3.2	Single station
2013-03-13T20:38:56.152000Z	14.920	35.202		2.8	Single station
2013-03-13T22:24:33.230000Z	15.394	35.408		2.5	Single station (poor)
2013-03-14T08:35:24.194000Z	15.256	35.400		3.3	Single station
2013-03-26T22:54:26.077000Z	14.551	35.737		2.0	Single station
2013-05-14T13:51:56.521000Z	15.075	36.337		3.5	Single station
2013-05-21T16:33:26.340000Z	15.166	36.173	28900.0	2.7	Network
2013-07-01T23:10:17.640000Z	16.255	35.800	37400.0	2.6	Network
2013-07-06T04:12:01.870000Z	14.530	35.677		2.1	Single station
2013-07-17T06:18:43.040000Z	14.580	34.131		3.2	Single station
2013-07-27T20:07:45.402000Z	14.881	35.989		2.7	Single station
2013-07-28T11:42:53.050000Z	15.597	36.255	31300.0	2.3	Network
2013-08-01T22:44:55.563000Z	14.853	36.030		2.2	Single station
2013-08-07T01:14:51.389000Z	15.445	35.913		2.3	Single station (poor)
2013-08-26T03:52:14.887000Z	14.886	35.005		2.9	Single station
2013-10-25T22:31:24.055000Z	14.844	35.584		2.3	Single station
2013-11-04T13:07:19.821000Z	13.626	35.358		2.9	Single station (poor)

2013-11-21T21:05:56.670000Z	16.374	35.325	30000.0	2.8	Network
2013-11-28T14:17:55.282000Z	14.869	34.727		2.8	Single station (poor)
2013-12-07T15:35:06.895000Z	13.501	35.128		3.1	Single station (poor)
2013-12-25T13:03:27.103000Z	14.818	34.801		3.0	Single station
2014-01-16T19:13:13.585000Z	14.599	35.739		2.3	Single station
2014-01-17T02:46:40.925000Z	14.560	35.721		2.1	Single station
2014-02-03T03:59:27.851000Z	14.915	35.613		2.8	Single station
2014-02-08T02:53:54.359000Z	15.296	34.494		3.3	Single station
2014-02-17T12:47:05.727000Z	13.928	35.698		2.6	Single station
2014-03-01T05:24:36.024000Z	14.888	35.636		2.5	Single station
2014-03-20T18:08:38.548000Z	13.816	35.539		2.5	Single station (poor)
2014-04-02T10:20:49.920000Z	13.617	36.331	23700.0	2.0	Network
2014-04-02T10:27:26.420000Z	13.511	36.397	31300.0	2.7	Network
2014-04-18T11:57:56.037000Z	14.201	35.707		2.4	Single station
2014-05-05T11:40:12.098000Z	14.593	35.521		2.4	Single station
2014-05-11T21:50:50.084000Z	14.161	34.532		3.3	Single station
2014-05-21T04:13:33.045000Z	14.782	35.479		4.0	Single station
2014-05-21T04:41:18.021000Z	14.479	35.460		2.9	Single station
2014-05-21T04:45:57.437000Z	14.614	35.469		2.7	Single station
2014-05-21T05:52:05.180000Z	14.848	35.541		3.2	Single station
2014-05-21T05:55:50.252000Z	14.524	35.471		2.5	Single station
2014-05-22T10:33:48.533000Z	14.664	35.544		2.4	Single station
2014-05-24T05:59:29.473000Z	14.827	35.566		2.9	Single station
2014-05-25T00:38:05.773000Z	14.734	35.491		2.7	Single station
2014-05-25T23:50:09.384000Z	14.541	35.451		2.6	Single station (poor)
2014-05-27T05:00:03.712000Z	14.877	35.588		3.0	Single station
2014-06-29T17:11:40.640000Z	14.060	36.350	28700.0	2.7	Network
2014-07-09T15:30:48.300000Z	14.063	35.863		2.2	Single station (poor)
2014-07-15T17:23:10.937000Z	14.899	35.617		2.6	Single station
2014-08-02T11:45:42.240000Z	13.731	35.177	10000.0	2.6	Network
2014-08-08T03:28:44.264000Z	14.988	35.684		2.4	Single station (poor)
2014-08-10T17:26:09.517000Z	13.924	36.369		2.5	Single station
2014-10-31T23:35:21.690000Z	13.511	36.291	86700.0	2.6	Network
2014-11-09T07:34:24.890000Z	13.896	36.396	25300.0	3.4	Network
2014-11-11T10:30:05.510000Z	14.297	36.266	9900.0	3.0	Network
2014-11-12T00:08:59.420000Z	14.279	36.306	10000.0	2.8	Network
2014-11-12T12:07:13.750000Z	14.252	36.321	10500.0	3.1	Network
2014-11-19T03:37:32.980000Z	13.574	36.354	22500.0	2.7	Network
2014-11-19T13:06:13.710000Z	13.502	36.363	32300.0	3.7	Network
2014-11-19T13:07:33.190000Z	13.643	36.314	22800.0	2.6	Network
2014-11-19T18:25:02.250000Z	13.581	36.359	19400.0	2.2	Network